

Energy and Exergy Analyses of Thin-Layer Drying of Pineapple Slices

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Abstract—Energy and exergy analyses of thin-layer drying of pineapple slices (*Ananas comosus* L.) were conducted in a laboratory tunnel dryer. Drying experiments were carried out at three temperatures (100, 115 and 130 °C) and at an air velocity of 1.45 m/s. The effects of drying variables on energy utilisation, energy utilisation ratio, exergy loss and exergy efficiency were studied. The enthalpy difference of the gas increased as the inlet gas temperature increase. It is observed that at the 75 minutes of the drying process the outlet gas enthalpy achieves a maximum value that is very close to the inlet value and remains constant until the end of the drying process. This behaviour is due to the reduction of the total enthalpy within the system, or in other words, the reduction of the effective heat transfer from the hot gas flow to the vegetable being dried. Further, the outlet entropy exhibits a significant increase that is not only due to the temperature variation, but also to the increase of water vapour phase contained in the hot gas flow. The maximum value of the exergy efficiency curve corresponds to the maximum value observed within the drying rate curves. This maximum value represents the stage when the available energy is efficiently used in the removal of the moisture within the solid. As the drying rate decreases the available energy is started to be less employed. The exergetic efficiency was directly dependent on the evaporation flux and since the convective drying is less efficient than other types of dryer, it is likely that the exergetic efficiency has relatively low values.

Keywords— Efficiency, Energy, Exergy, Pineapple, Thin-layer drying.

I. INTRODUCTION

PINEAPPLE (*Ananas comosus* L.) is an herbaceous perennial plant and is believed to be originated from South America, in the region encompassing central and southern Brazil, northern Argentina and Paraguay. Pineapple is the third most important tropical fruit in the international trade after bananas and citrus [1]. Currently, pineapples are harvested commercially in several countries, such as Nicaragua, Mexico, Philippines, India, Indonesia, and Thailand, amongst others. Pineapple is a good source of carbohydrate, fibre, and minerals especially Ca, P, Fe, Na and K. It also contains some vitamins including A, B1 (thiamine),

B2 (riboflavin), B3 (niacin), B5 (pantothenic acid), B6 (pyridoxine), B9 (folate) and C (ascorbic acid). The nutritional content is influenced by several factors including varieties, soil, climatic condition, maturity stage and handling [1].

Convective drying, especially tray drying, has been widely used as a method for preserving many vegetables and fruits, including pineapple, at various conditions. For instance, Agarry *et al.* [2] observed that the drying rates and drying time of pineapple slices are affected by the blanching temperature-time combinations. In general, blanching of pineapple slices improved the drying and effective diffusivity. Olanipekun *et al.* [3] reported that the drying process occurred only in falling rate period for all the experimental conditions studied. The predictions obtained using the two-term model, parabolic and Page models were in good agreement with experimental data obtained for hot-air, microwave and sun drying of pineapple, respectively. Ravula *et al.* [4] determined the energy consumption and exergy efficiency of thin-layer drying of pineapple. An increase in drying air temperature affected the specific energy requirement and exergy efficiency of the drying process.

Recently, several studies have been undertaken on energy and exergy analyses of food drying, however, information on the energy and exergy analyses of pineapples drying appear to be scanty in the scientific literature. The main objective of this study was to investigate the energetics and exergetics of pineapples drying in a tunnel dryer at different drying air temperatures.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Material

Fresh pineapples were procured from a local vegetable market and then washed with tap water and grouped. Prior to drying, pineapple pointed ends were trimmed, peeled-off, and sliced. The samples did not include the central axis, only the pulp material. The pineapple pulps were cut into rectangular slices [5].

B. Experimental Apparatus

A schematic arrangement of the experimental apparatus is shown in Fig. 1. The equipment may be divided into four main sections as follows: gas supply and dehumidification section, heating section, drying chamber, and analysing equipment. The blower (B) supplies a gas flow—a broad range of flow rates are possible by changing the rpm setting through the frequency inverter (FI). The air passes through an adsorption column (AC) containing a dehumidificant (silica gel) to obtain

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a process air of low humidity content (less than 1.0 % relative humidity) measured by a hygrometer. The air velocity is measured by an anemometer. After dehumidification, the air is pre-heated with electrical resistance (ER) heaters of up to 2 kW each. Temperature is controlled by means of a temperature controller (TC) that supplies heat by means of an electrical resistance heater as its final control element. Before entering the drying chamber, a static mixer homogenises temperature by mixing the gas. The sample is put in a sample

holder (SH) inside the drying chamber and is supported on a weighing balance (WB) through an oil-sealed shaft. The cross-sectional area and depth of sample holder are 30.65 mm × 109.8 mm and 3 mm, respectively. The drying chamber has a uniform cross-sectional area of 90 mm × 110 mm. The sample's weight history is recorded on a computer (C). It is possible to take a reading every 12 seconds [6].

Fig. 1 A schematic diagram of a tunnel drying system.

C. Experimental Procedure

The experiments were performed at an air velocity of 1.5 m/s and at three temperatures: 100, 115, and 130 °C. Before starting an experiment, the apparatus was run for at least half an hour to obtain steady-state conditions. The sample was loaded evenly in the sample holder, which covered the whole drying area as a thin-layer. The sample holder was put into the tunnel dryer. The drying time and mass of the sample were recorded. The test was stopped until the mass was invariable. After drying by the apparatus above, the sample was further dried in an oven at 105 °C for 24 hours to determine its oven-dry mass (m_d). The initial mass, drying mass and oven-dry mass were determined with a precise analytical balance. Temperature and humidity of the air were measured employing a Testo® thermal hygrometer. The solid surface temperature was directly measured employing a thermocouple connected to the computer (C). All the drying experiments were performed in triplicate. Post-processing of these data yields the drying kinetics [5,6].

D. Drying Kinetics

The moisture content was computed as follows:

$$X_i = X_{i-1} + \frac{1}{m_s} \left(\frac{m_i - m_{i-1}}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where X is the moisture content at any time (on a dry basis), m is the mass of the sample at any time, and t is the time. The drying rate is defined as:

$$N_v = -\frac{m_s}{A_s} \frac{dX}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where N_v is the drying rate at any time and A_s is the drying area. Using the moisture content data as a function of time and a centred approximation of the derivative, it is possible to determine the drying rate as follows [7]:

$$N_v(X_i) = -\frac{m_s}{A_s(X_i)} \left(\frac{X_{i+1} - X_{i-1}}{t_{i+1} - t_{i-1}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The processing of the experimental data is performed using a program written in MATLAB®, this program reads the experimental data obtained and plots the drying curves and drying rate curves according to Eqs. (1) and (3).

The characteristic drying curve (CDC) concept, firstly introduced by van Meel [8], relies on an appropriate transformation of the drying rate curve coordinates to look for a single normalised drying rate curve, which does not depend on external parameters (e.g., air conditions).

E. Energy Analysis

The data obtained from drying experiments were used to perform the energy analysis of the pineapple drying process. Drying process was considered as a steady flow process and from the first law of thermodynamics, for an open system, the energy balance can be written as follows:

$$\dot{Q} = \sum \dot{m}_{g,o} h_o - \sum \dot{m}_{g,i} h_i \quad (4)$$

where \dot{Q} is the heat energy inflow, \dot{m} is the mass flow, and h is the enthalpy. The subscripts o , i , g denote inlet, outlet, and gas, respectively. By assuming the equality of entering and leaving the mass flow rates of the drying system ($\dot{m}_{g,o} = \dot{m}_{g,i}$), Eq. (4) can be written as follows [9]:

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{m}_g (h_o - h_i) = \dot{m}_g \Delta h \quad (5)$$

The enthalpy of the drying air is calculated as:

$$h = c_{p,g} T_g + \lambda w \quad (6)$$

where c_p is the specific heat, T is the temperature, λ is the latent heat of vaporisation, and w is the humidity ratio.

F. Exergy Analysis

Exergy analysis of the drying process was carried out based on the second law of thermodynamics, which asserts that energy has quality as well as quantity, and that actual process occurs in the direction decreasing quality of energy [9]. The second law notes that part of the exergy entering a thermal system is destroyed within the system due to irreversibilities. In the light of the above postulation, the total exergy inflow, outflow, and losses of the drying process were estimated. The basic procedure followed was to determine the exergy values at steady-state points using the properties the working medium from the first law energy balance. For this purpose, the mathematical formulations used to carry out the exergy balance are, for an open system, as follows:

$$E_x = c_{p,g} \left[(T_g - T_\infty) - T_\infty \ln \frac{T_g}{T_\infty} \right] \quad (7)$$

where E_x is the exergy and ∞ denotes ambient condition. Equation (10) can be used to calculate the exergy inflow and outflow at the inlet and outlet temperatures, respectively. Then, the exergy loss throughout the process is determined using the following expression:

$$\text{Exergy loss} = \text{Exergy inflow} - \text{Exergy outflow} \quad (8)$$

$$\sum E_{x,L} = \sum E_{x,i} - \sum E_{x,o} \quad (9)$$

where L denotes loss. The exergetic efficiency has been defined as the ration of exergy outflow in the drying of the product to exergy of the drying air supplied to the system. This is given by the expression:

$$\text{Exergy efficiency} = \frac{\text{Exergy inflow} - \text{Exergy loss}}{\text{Exergy inflow}} \quad (10)$$

or

$$\text{Exergy efficiency} = 1 - \frac{\text{Exergy loss}}{\text{Exergy inflow}} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) can be stated as:

$$\eta_x = 1 - \frac{E_{x,L}}{E_{x,o}} \quad (12)$$

where η_x is exergy efficiency.

G. Entropy Balance

The general entropy balance is expressed as function of the mass flows (the input and output flows), their entropies, and the transferred heat through the walls of the drying chamber. This heat can have negative or positive signs, depending upon the heat transferred to or from the control volume, in this case the dryer [9].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Drying Kinetics

Drying rate was estimated based on Eq. (3) and its changes with moisture content are as shown in Fig. 2. An important influence of air-drying temperature on drying rate is observed in the curves. As expected, an increase in the drying air temperature increases the drying rate because higher air temperature causes a higher reduction of moisture content – in other words, at high temperatures the transfer of heat and mass is high, and liquid (water) loss is excessive.

Fig. 2 Drying rate curves for various temperatures at an air velocity of 1.5 m/s.

As can be seen from Fig. 2, one (1) drying rate period (i.e., falling rate period) was observed in the drying of pineapples. These results are in good agreement with earlier observations [2,4,10].

The drying rate and moisture content are normalised by the constant drying rate and critical moisture content, respectively. However, for pineapple no constant drying rate period was observed, and another approach must be found to normalise the drying data. In this case, the critical moisture content and the maximum drying rate were determined at the beginning of the falling rate period [7,11]. In Fig. 3, experimental drying data are plotted to represent $f = f(\phi)$. Figure (3) shows that all drying curves obtained with the characteristic moisture content (ϕ) and relative drying rate (f), for the different tested conditions, fall into a tight band, thus indicating that the effect of variation in different conditions is small over the range tested.

Fig. 3 Characteristic drying curve for pineapple.

The regression analysis was performed using MatLab®'s Curve Fitting Tool to find the best equation for the pineapple characteristics drying curve. A polynomial equation was found to fit the best the experimental data:

$$f = A\phi^5 + B\phi^4 + C\phi^3 + D\phi^2 + E\phi + F \quad (13)$$

where A, B, C, D, E, and F are 5.1691, -17.8962, 24.2952, -17.4471, 7.5861, and -0.7215, respectively.

The changes in temperature for pineapple and air along the drying process are shown in Fig. 4. In the first 20 minutes, pineapple exhibits a steep increase in temperature. Then, a period of slow increase is observed during the following 60 minutes, which is because moisture (water) to be evaporated comes from within the pineapple pulp structure and must be transported to the surface. Further, a linear behaviour is observed in which moisture transported from within the pineapple pulp structure did not show resistance to heat transfer, thus allowing the temperature to remain constant until the end of the drying process. The outlet air flow is greater than the inlet air flow due to the absorption of the evaporated moisture (water) leaving the pineapple pulp structure during the drying process.

Fig. 4 Temperature curves for pineapple at an air temperature of 100 °C and 1.45 m/s.

B. Energy Analysis

The enthalpy variation during the drying of pineapple was measured to determine the time that takes to reach its maximum enthalpy value and the characteristics of its curve (see Fig. 5), which is the amount of energy transferred from the hot air flow to the pineapple necessary for moisture removal.

Fig. 5 Enthalpy at an air temperature of 100 °C and 1.45 m/s.

In Fig.5, the enthalpy of the gas experienced an increase over time according to its respective increase in temperature. It was noted that at the 75 minutes, the outlet gas enthalpy reached a maximum value very close to the inlet value and remained constant until the end of the process. Consequently, the $-\Delta h$ values (not shown here) decrease. This behaviour is due to the reduction of the total enthalpy within the system, or in other words, the reduction of the effective heat transfer of the hot air flow to the

pineapple. This phenomenon occurs because, after contact with hot air, the pineapple's temperature reaches its equilibrium state. In this equilibrium, the temperature of the wet pineapple surface is the same as the wet bulb of the drying air, this is when the maximum enthalpy point is reached because the critical moisture content is reached. Then as the moisture content decreases and the surface moisture dries (evaporation) more than the water being transporting to the surface from within the pineapple pulp structure (mass transfer), thus allowing the enthalpy to remain constant because the pineapple reached the equilibrium with drying conditions.

C. Entropy

The entropy variation is shown in Fig. 6. As observed, the entropy variation exhibits a similar behaviour to the enthalpy variation. In this case, entropy is calculated because it serves to measure the degree of disorder within a process and allows to distinguish useful energy, which is what is converted into work entirely, from useless energy, which is lost in the environment.

Fig. 6 Entropy at an air temperature of 100 °C and 1.45 m/s.

It was noted that the entropy calculated at the dryer outlet experiences a significant increase not only due to the temperature variation, but also to the increase of the water vapour phase within the hot air flow because of evaporation of the moisture content. For this reason, there is a short stage in which the outlet entropy slightly increases with respect with the inlet entropy. As a result of this particularity, the $-\Delta s$ of the system (gas stream) falls slightly (not shown here). By remaining nearly constant after the 80 minutes, the ability to generate useful energy is lost or transformed into other less usable energy. The point of the least degree of system disorder is reached. Alfaro [5] reported a similar experimentally behaviour for tomato thin-layer drying.

D. Exergy Analysis

The exergy variation is shown in Fig. 7. By observing the exergy over time, the quality of the energy is determined and at what exact stage the maximum exergy is reached (maximum energy quality). In this case, the exergy value is 1.6981 kW. Further, the available outlet energy has a significant increase because only in the first stage (ascending stage) is efficiently used in moisture evaporation. The pineapple at 80 minutes begins to remain slightly constant near its maximum exergy value, while tomato at 40 minutes [5]. It means that the tomato is exergetically efficient since in 40 minutes less than pineapple reaches its highest point of conversion of useful energy into pure work, thus providing a higher value of energy quality.

Fig. 7 Exergy at an air temperature of 100 °C and 1.45 m/s.

E. Exergy Efficiency

The variation in exergy efficiency over time was calculated (see Fig. 8) to determine the stage in which the pineapple and drying conditions could be improved to gradually eliminate the irreversibilities of the drying process and improve the use of available energy in useful energy.

A fourth order polynomial fit has been used to understand the trend of η_x because the evaporation rate data shows experimental noise. The polynomial equation was found to fit the best the experimental data is:

$$\eta_x = A_1 t^5 + A_2 t^4 + A_3 t^3 + A_4 t^2 + A_5 t + A_6 \quad (14)$$

where A_1 , A_2 , A_3 , A_4 , and A_5 are 2×10^{-13} , -1×10^{-10} , 4×10^{-8} , -5×10^{-6} , 0.003, and 0.0019, respectively.

The efficiency variation trend is directly related to the drying rate curves of pineapple. The maximum value of the efficiency curve corresponds to the maximum value that can be observed within drying rate curves. This maximum value represents the stage when the available energy is

efficiently used in the removal of moisture content. As the drying rate decreases, the available energy begins to be less used. This can also be deduced by observing in a complementary way the Fig. 7.

Fig. 8 Exergy efficiency at an air temperature of 100 °C and 1.45 m/s.

It must be considered that hot air drying is the one that has, among all the other drying methods, the highest exergy losses due to the hot air outlet, little exergy is introduced during the process to the solid to be dried and there are a few losses in the walls of the dryer due to its size even when it is insulated. It also influences that the dryer is experimental and the sample to be dried is small compared to the dimensions of the dryer. Analysing the conditions and the dryer with the theory, it is found that increasing the mass flow of the solid decreases the exergy. Increasing the mass flow of the inlet air does not significantly affect the exergy, therefore the optimal flow must be used and calculated to increase the exergy efficiency. The exergy increases by increasing the mass of the solid to be dried, as this experiment was carried out with an experimental dryer, in which very large air flows are usually used with respect to the water to be evaporated, low exergy efficiency values emerged. However, in the design of an industrial dryer, an appropriate relationship between the flow of air and the water to be evaporated must be considered for a better use of the available energy.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Energy and exergy analyses of thin-layer drying of pineapple (*Ananas comosus* L.) were conducted in a tunnel dryer at a constant air velocity of 1.45 m/s and temperatures of 100, 115, and 130 °C. Pineapple did not observe a constant drying rate period under the experimental conditions employed and showed only a falling drying rate period. Further, a non-linear regression procedure was used to determine the characteristic drying curve. The enthalpy

variation of the gas increased as the inlet gas temperature increase. It was observed that at the 75 minutes of the drying process, the outlet gas enthalpy reached a maximum value that is very close to the inlet value and remained constant until the end of the process. This behaviour is due to the reduction of the total enthalpy within the system, or in other words, the reduction of the effective heat transfer of the hot air flow to the pineapple. In addition, the outlet entropy exhibits a significant increase that is not only due to the temperature variation, but also to the increase of the water vapour phase within the hot air flow. The maximum value of the exergy efficiency curve corresponds to the maximum value observed within drying rate curves. This maximum value represents the stage when the available energy is efficiently used in moisture removal. As the drying rate decreases the available energy is started to be less employed. The exergetic efficiency was directly dependent on the evaporation flux and since the convective drying is less efficient than other types of dryer, it is likely that the exergetic efficiency has relatively low values.

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